

category diagrams.tex

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Diagrams

1.
$$\begin{array}{ccc} A & \xrightarrow{f} & B \\ \alpha \downarrow & & \beta \downarrow \\ A' & \xrightarrow{g} & B' \end{array}$$

2.
$$\begin{array}{ccc} & A & \\ f \swarrow & & \searrow g \\ B & \xrightarrow{\alpha} & C \end{array}$$

3.
$$\begin{array}{ccc} B & \xrightarrow{\alpha} & C \\ f \searrow & & \swarrow g \\ & A & \end{array}$$

4.
$$\begin{array}{ccc} & A & \\ f \swarrow & \xrightarrow{h} & \searrow g \\ X & \xrightarrow{i} & Y \end{array}$$

5.
$$\begin{array}{ccc} & A & \\ g \swarrow & \xleftarrow{k} & \swarrow h \\ X & \xrightarrow{i} & Y \end{array}$$

